

Assessing the Performance of Biopolymers as Substrates for Flexible Printed Supercapacitors Containing Liquid Electrolytes

Iida Kangashaka, Timo Punkari, Aapo Kattainen, Chirag Mevada, Jari Keskinen, Matti Mäntysalo, and Essi Sarlin*

The environmental benefits of using supercapacitors to power the Internet of Things can be improved by replacing the fossil-based substrate materials that they are traditionally manufactured from with sustainable biobased options. However, biobased materials tend to have poor barrier properties, which is an issue for supercapacitors that contain a liquid electrolyte. The aim of this study is to assess how well some common biobased polymers, such as polylactic acid (PLA), poly(3-hydroxybutyrate) (PHB), or poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) (PHBV) would perform as substrates in printed supercapacitors, especially when it comes to their barrier properties. It is found that none of the unmodified biopolymers fulfill the requirements for the supercapacitors very well. The processability of the materials is good and the printability of the biopolymers is even better than the printability of the polyethylene terephthalate laminated with aluminum (PET+Al) used as a reference material. However, the barrier properties of the biopolymers do not reach the properties required of a supercapacitor operating in a vehicle. For this reason, it is clear that in order to manufacture a sustainable substrate suitable for a supercapacitor, the biobased polymers must be first modified in order to improve their barrier properties.

require wiring into outlets or routinely either recharging or changing batteries.^[1] For devices which must remain untethered, self-charging power systems are an attractive option for power supply.^[2]

They are a combination of energy harvesters and energy-storage units. The system harvests ambient energy, such as radiant, mechanical, thermal, or biochemical energy, from the environment and stores it in an energy-storage unit, such as a battery, a supercapacitor (SC), or a pseudocapacitor.^[2]

Among these, SCs stand out due to their moderate energy density, high power density, superior operational safety, and long lifetimes. Unlike batteries, which offer high energy density but require significant recharging time, SCs provide flexibility, smaller size, transparency, and ease of integration, making them ideal for a wide range of flexible, portable, and wearable electronic devices. SCs can operate at extremely high charging and discharging rates, with life-

times exceeding 1 million cycles.^[3] The absence of rigid packaging in SCs, combined with their high rate and long cycle life, is crucial for various applications. The most common type of SC is a sandwich-structured SC, which consists of electrolyte sandwiched between two electrodes, which are separated by a separator to prevent contact and, in case of nonconductive substrates, coated with current collectors (Figure 1).^[1]

When it comes to fabricating SCs, traditional manufacturing methods, such as solution casting, electrospinning, spin coating, sputtering, electrochemical deposition, and chemical vapor deposition, face challenges like process complexity, extended production times, high costs, and low material utilization rates. These conventional techniques also struggle with miniaturization and customization, which are essential for the growing demand for wearable and flexible energy devices. In recent years, printing technologies like screen printing, inkjet printing, and direct ink writing have emerged as promising methods for fabricating SCs. These technologies offer rapid prototyping, customizability, material diversity, process flexibility, and precise geometry control.^[4]

Additionally, there is a high demand for low-cost, nontoxic, eco-friendly, and biodegradable SCs, driven by the expected increase in e-waste to 74.7 million tons by 2030. To address these challenges, the development of fully biodegradable and printed

1. Introduction

For a while now there has been a shift in the field of electronics toward the connection of everyday objects through the Internet of Things.^[1] However, in some cases it can be difficult to provide power for these devices in the traditional methods, as this would

I. Kangashaka, E. Sarlin
Materials Science and Environmental Engineering
Tampere University
P.O. Box 589, Tampere FI-33014, Finland
E-mail: iida.kangashaka@tuni.fi

T. Punkari, A. Kattainen, C. Mevada, J. Keskinen, M. Mäntysalo
Faculty of Information Technology and Communication Sciences
Tampere University
Tampere FI-33014, Finland

 The ORCID identification number(s) for the author(s) of this article can be found under <https://doi.org/10.1002/aesr.202500330>.

© 2025 The Author(s). Advanced Energy and Sustainability Research published by Wiley-VCH GmbH. This is an open access article under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

DOI: 10.1002/aesr.202500330

Figure 1. Schematic of the cross section of a sandwich-structured SC.^[36]

SCs is essential.^[5] This approach makes them ideal for powering eco-friendly and disposable devices. It is essential to ensure that all components of SCs are biobased and environmentally sustainable while employing cost-effective printing technologies as an alternative to conventional manufacturing methods. The commercial SCs still use metal current collectors, but replacing these with biodegradable options is possible. For printed electronics, various biobased substrates combined with printing of high-conductive carbon ink (sheet resistance $\leq 10 \Omega/\square$) can replace the use of metal current collectors, promoting sustainability in flexible printed SCs. Common polymeric substrates used in printed SCs include polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polyimide, polyethylene naphthalate, and polydimethylsiloxane, with PET being the most common of these.^[1] However, all of these polymers are fossil-based and nonbiodegradable. A more sustainable option would be to choose biobased polymers as the substrates instead, but, to the best knowledge of the authors, biobased polymers have not yet been studied as substrate materials of SCs containing liquid electrolytes. Potential biobased substrate materials include polymers such as polylactic acid (PLA), poly(3-hydroxybutyrate) (PHB), or poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) (PHBV). They are all produced through bacterial fermentation from sources such as sugar and starch.^[6–8] PLA degrades primarily through hydrolysis, which happens quite slowly compared to other biodegradable polymers, after months of contact with moisture,^[6] whereas PHB and PHBV degrade in conditions where they are in contact with micro-organisms.^[7,8] The chemical structures of PLA, PHB, PHBV, and PET are shown in **Figure 2**.

The most important property of the substrate of a sandwich-structured SC is its barrier against the electrolyte. A certain minimum amount of the electrolyte must remain within the SC for it to function, so the substrate should prevent it from evaporating to lengthen the device's lifetime. PET is the most common fossil-based polymeric substrate for SCs due to its good barrier properties against moisture and relatively low cost.^[1] The barrier

properties of PET are often further improved by laminating it with a layer of aluminum. PLA is the most commonly used biopolymer, but compared to conventional fossil-based polymers it has inferior barrier properties and is quite brittle.^[6] PHB and PHBV have good barrier properties against moisture and gases and have physical and mechanical properties close to conventional fossil-based polymers due to their high crystallinities, though PHBV tends to be more rigid and brittle than PHB.^[7,8]

Despite their differences, PLA, PHB, and PHBV are used in very similar applications. Due to their biocompatibility and bioresorbability, they are used in biomedical applications, such as screws, plates, surgical sutures, scaffolds for tissue engineering, and controlled drug delivery systems.^[6,9,10] Their biodegradability also makes them an option for agricultural applications, such as mulch films.^[6,9,10] However, it has been shown that the addition of PHB or PHBV in soil could negatively affect soil and plant health.^[11,12] PLA, PHB, and PHBV have all also been presented as options for disposable food packaging applications.^[6,9,10] Additionally, all three are suitable materials for fiber production for textile applications.^[6,9,10]

The aim of this study was to evaluate how well PLA, PHB, and PHBV fulfill the requirements for substrate materials of printed sandwich-structured SCs with liquid electrolyte used to power various applications compared to aluminum laminated PET (PET+Al) by assessing their behavior during the processing and printing of the SC, as well as their suitability for the application during the lifetime of the SC. The intention is to find a biobased substrate with properties as good as PET+Al, even without the aluminum layer, which is why only the reference material has the aluminum coating. The materials' processing characteristics are studied through their thermal properties, mechanical properties, and necking. Printability is estimated by way of surface energy and the adhesion between the printed ink and SC substrates to assess the compatibility of the substrate and ink layers in varying temperature conditions. The polymers' suitability as the substrates of a SC and the longevity of the SC's lifetime are assessed through their absorption and barrier properties.

Figure 2. Molecular structures of A) PLA, B) PHB, C) PHBV, and D) PET.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Processability

2.1.1. Thermal Properties

The extrusion conditions of a polymer film are largely dependent on the material's thermal properties, as the polymer should melt

or soften without degradation during processing. For semicrystalline polymers, the processing temperature window is between the melting temperature (T_m) and the thermal degradation temperature (T_d) of the material. For amorphous polymers, the window is between the glass transition temperature (T_g) and T_d , as T_g is where the polymer begins to flow. However, the viscosity of the polymer right above the T_g is too high for extrusion, and in reality, the processing window of an amorphous polymer is narrower. The thermal properties of the selected polymers were determined through differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA), and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and are shown in **Table 1**. Out of PET, PHB, and PHBV, which are all semicrystalline polymers, PET has the largest processing window. The T_g and T_m measured here for PET are aligned well with literature values.^[13] PHB and PHBV both melt and degrade at much lower temperatures compared to PET. When it comes to their thermal properties, PHB and PHBV are very similar, with the T_g , T_m , and T_d of PHBV being only slightly below those of PHB. The smaller processing windows of PHB and PHBV mean that processing temperatures must be chosen more carefully compared to PET. On the other hand, PHB and PHBV can be processed at much lower temperatures, which saves energy. The T_m 's of PHB and PHBV determined here were very well aligned with the values found in literature for ENMAT Y3000 and ENMAT Y1000.^[14–17] This was also the case for the values of T_d found in the literature.^[14,16,17] However, the T_g values found in the literature for PHB (5–8 °C^[14,15]) and PHBV (–3–2 °C^[16,17]) were very different from the values determined here, likely due to the fact that literature values were determined with DSC whereas the values here were determined with DMA. The T_g and T_m values found in the literature for ENMAT Y3000 and ENMAT Y1000 also aligned well with the literature values found for PHB and PHBV in general.^[8,18] Based on the T_g and T_d , the processing window of the amorphous PLA is quite large, but as mentioned, amorphous polymers do not become processable immediately above T_g . The recommended melt processing temperature of the PLA in this study according to its technical data sheet is 210 °C,^[19] which is approximately halfway between the measured T_g and T_d of PLA. The values of T_g and T_d determined for PLA here match well with ones found in literature for Ingeo 4060D,^[20,21] and the T_g also matches well with general results for PLA.^[6] DSC was also used to determine the crystallinities of the polymers, apart from the amorphous PLA. The crystallinities of PHB and PHBV are significantly higher than

that of PET. This is likely due to the higher flexibility of the PHB and PHBV chains compared to PET. A polymer's ability to form crystals is affected by its ability to fold itself into the crystal structure, and bulky groups on the polymer backbone or side groups hinder this ability. The phenylene group in PET is very bulky and would inhibit crystallinity significantly.

2.1.2. Necking

Necking is the reduction in width of the extruded film as it exits the die. The necking of the biopolymers extruded in the laboratory was measured and is shown in Table 1. Necking is quite significant for all of the biopolymers studied here. For PHBV, necking was approximately half of the film's width, and for PLA and PHB it was even higher, 60.1%. Necking can affect the choice of roll size in roll-to-roll processing, as the films are narrower than expected and so narrower rolls can be used.

2.1.3. Mechanical Properties

Tensile properties are important to know for good web handling during roll-to-roll processing. The results of tensile testing are shown in **Figure 3** (Table S1, Supporting Information). The rule of thumb for web tension is 10–25% of the film's strength in the machine direction, where the upper limit aims to protect the web from breaking, and the lower limit ensures that the tension is high enough to keep the web flat.^[22] For the substrates studied here, the maximum stress of the material was often also the breaking stress, and so the strength and stress at break are essentially the same. PHB and PHBV, which have near identical tensile properties compared to each other, are the polymers with the lowest strength. This would make the PHB and PHBV films the hardest to tension correctly, as the range of suitable tension values is the smallest. PLA's strength is approximately twice as high as those of PHB and PHBV. The strengths of PLA, PHB, and PHBV measured here align well with the values found in literature for Ingeo 4060D, ENMAT Y3000, and ENMAT Y1000,^[15–17,23–25] as well as for PLA, PHB, and PHBV in general.^[6,8,18] The lower strength of PHB and PHBV could be caused by their higher crystallinities making them more brittle. PET+Al is the strongest of the films and the one with the widest range of possible web tension values. However, during the tensile test the brittle aluminum layer of PET+Al split into small "islands" along the surface of the PET as it continued to stretch. For this reason,

Table 1. Glass transition temperatures (T_g), melting temperatures (T_m), and thermal degradation temperatures (T_d) of PLA, PHB, PHBV, and PET+Al. Processing windows of the polymers based on the thermal properties, enthalpies of melting (ΔH_m), crystallinities, and necking values for the biopolymers extruded in the laboratory. Representative DSC and TGA curves given in Figure S1 and S2, Supporting Information.

Polymer	T_g [°C]	T_m [°C]	T_d [°C]	Processing window [°C]	ΔH_m [J g ⁻¹]	Crystallinity [%]	Necking [%]
PLA	56 ± 0.2	NA	339 ± 0.9	282 ^{b)}	NA	NA	60.1 ± 1.5
PHB	50 ^{a)}	173 ± 0.4	283 ± 0.1	110	100 ± 0.4	68	60.1 ± 1.8
PHBV	48 ^{a)}	170 ± 0.0	281 ± 2.6	111	89 ± 4.7	61	50.4 ± 2.8
PET+Al	71 ± 0.3	251 ± 0.3	410 ± 0.9	159	29 ± 0.6	21	NA

^{a)}Only one sample was measured, so no standard deviation is included. ^{b)}For PLA, the processing window is between T_g and T_d , whereas for the other polymers the window is between T_m and T_d .

Figure 3. Tensile properties of PLA, PHB, PHBV, and PET+Al. Representative stress–strain curves given in Figure S3, Supporting Information.

the tensile properties are much more dependent on the PET layer, while still being slightly supported by the aluminum layer. This is presumably why the strength given for PET in literature (53 MPa)^[13] is much lower than the value determined here, since the aluminum layer helps support the PET layer and increase the strength. The films' tensile properties also affect how tightly the film can be wound onto a roll at the end of the processing line. Stretchable films with low modulus are much easier to wind tightly, whereas stiffer materials are more difficult to wind correctly, which can lead to defects, such as wrinkling.^[22] All of the substrates have quite high moduli, PHBV being the material with the lowest stiffness. PET+Al has the highest modulus, making it the stiffest material, likely due to the supporting effect of the aluminum layer. The tensile modulus for PLA matches quite well with literature values (2129–3100 MPa^[23,24]), but both PHB and PHBV have moduli below the literature values (3510,^[15] 3671–4000 MPa,^[16,17] respectively). The strain at break values determined here for PLA, PHB, and PHBV match quite well with the values found in literature for Ingeo 4060D, ENMAT Y3000, and ENMAT Y1000,^[15–17,24] as well as for PLA, PHB, and PHBV in general.^[6,8,18] The strain found in the literature for PET

(300%)^[13] is higher than the value found here, likely due to the way the aluminum layer breaks during stretching, since the stress presumably focuses on the parts of the film between the “islands” where the PET is not supported by the aluminum. Additionally, the mechanical properties discussed here only determine the roll-to-roll processability of the plain film before the electrical elements are printed. The printed and dried ink layers are quite brittle, so their mechanical strength will be the deciding factor when deciding the correct winding tightness for the printed films.

Flexural properties (Figure 4, Table S1, Supporting Information) are also important when it comes to processing. Especially during roll-to-roll processing, where films experience bending stress as they are wound onto rolls. It is common for the flexural strength of a material to be higher than the tensile strength of the same material.^[26,27] That is the case here for both PHB and PHBV. However, for PLA and PET+Al, tensile strength is higher. For PET+Al, this is likely because aluminum films are flexible but not stretchable, so the supporting effect would be more significant in tension. For PLA it is possible that the film has some defects on the surface. Since during bending

Figure 4. Flexural properties of PLA, PHB, PHBV, and PET+Al. Representative stress–strain curves given in Figure S4, Supporting Information.

the tensile and compressive stresses are at their highest on the surfaces, if the surface is weakened by defects, flexural strength might be lower than tensile strength. The flexural strength values for PLA and PHB are slightly lower than literature values for Ingeo 4060D and ENMAT Y3000 (100.15^[24] and 65.8 MPa,^[15] respectively), whereas PHBV's value is slightly lower than that of ENMAT Y1000 in literature (26.79 MPa^[28]). The flexural moduli are also higher than the tensile moduli. As before, PHBV has the lowest modulus and is the most flexible, and PET+Al has the highest modulus. Based on just the modulus, PET+Al film seems like an incredibly stiff material. However, the thickness of the film also plays a role in flexibility, and since PET+Al was the thinnest of the films, it is also very flexible when handled. PLA and PHB's flexural modulus values match quite well with values found from the literature, but PHBV's modulus is slightly lower (2868.7,^[24] 3542,^[15] and 1540 MPa,^[28] respectively).

The mechanical properties also affect the substrate's durability during its lifetime, though it was not specifically tested here. This is especially notable for PET+Al due to its fragile aluminum layer. If the film experiences cyclic bending during its lifetime, it is possible for the aluminum layer to fracture or even delaminate from the PET.

Overall, the processability of the biopolymers is significantly limited compared to PET. PHB and PHBV have much narrower temperature ranges, where they are extrudable, than PET. And in roll-to-roll processing, the biopolymers have a much smaller ranges of possible web tension values than PET. Additionally, the considerable necking of the biopolymer films might set constraints on how wide the produced films can be.

2.2. Printability

2.2.1. Surface Energy

The surface energies of the substrate and the ink determine how well the printed ink spreads onto the surface. If the surface energy of the substrate is higher than that of the ink, the ink droplet wets the surface better. Good wetting is important for the formation of continuous ink layers. The surface energies of the inks used in inkjet printing are in the range of 25–50 mN m⁻¹.^[29] The surface energies of the films, which were calculated from the contact angles measured with a drop shape analyzer (Table S2, Supporting Information), are shown in **Figure 5**. Compared to the total surface energy of the reference material PET+Al (29 mN m⁻¹), PHBV and especially PHB have much lower total surface energies, 25 mN m⁻¹ and 21 mN m⁻¹, respectively. These values are at the lower end of the inks' surface energy range, which might cause problems with finding an ink formulation that can wet the substrate surface well without any surface treatments to the substrate. PLA's total surface energy (34 mN m⁻¹) is higher than that of PET+Al, which indicates finding a suitable ink will be easier. In addition to the total surface energy, the ratio of the dispersive and polar components also affects the wetting of the ink and its adhesion with the substrate. The more similar the ratio of dispersive and polar components of the substrate is to that of the ink, the more interactions there will be between them, which improves wetting and adhesion. The percentage of the polar component out of the total surface energy was calculated for the sake of comparing the substrates. The

Figure 5. Total, dispersive, and polar surface energies of PLA, PHB, PHBV, and PET+Al based on the Owens–Wendt–Rabel–Kaelble method.

polar component makes up 67%, 5%, 61%, and 36% of the total surface energy for PLA, PHB, PHBV, and PET+Al, respectively. The best biobased substrate alternative for an ink that would work for the reference material PET+Al would be PHBV, whose relative polar component is the closest to that of PET+Al. However, PHBV's surface energy is dominated by the polar component, whereas for PET+Al the dispersive component is dominant. The only biopolymer where the dispersive component is also dominant is PHB.

2.2.2. Adhesion

Proper adhesion between the substrate and the current collector is very important for the functioning of the SC, to prevent the printed layer from peeling off prematurely. The ASTM 3359-17 tape test assesses the adhesion based on how much of the ink is left after peeling off the tape and gives the sample a classification from 0B to 5B, with 5B indicating a test where no ink is removed. Only 5B is considered sufficient adhesion, as any amount of ink coming loose during the SC's lifetime would compromise its ability to function correctly. The adhesion classifications for the substrates are given in **Table 2**. The biopolymers performed very well, as the adhesion between the substrate and the ink was perfect for PHB and PHBV and near perfect for PLA. The reference material PET+Al had the worst average adhesion, and it also varied quite significantly, which was not the case for any of the biopolymers.

Based on these results it can be seen that the printability of the biobased substrates varies. PLA's total surface energy is more likely to encourage proper wetting of the ink, but its ratio of

Table 2. Adhesion classifications of PLA, PHB, PHBV, and PET+Al based on ASTM 3359-17 tape tests.

Polymer	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3
PLA	5B	4B	5B
PHB	5B	5B	5B
PHBV	5B	5B	5B
PET+Al	2B	5B	4B

dispersive to polar component is less likely to match with any ink that would be suitable for printing onto the reference material PET+Al, and its adhesion with a carbon ink is not adequate. On the other hand, PHB and PHBV have perfect adhesion with the carbon ink and the ratio of dispersive to polar component of their surface energies is better matched with any ink that would have good wetting and adhesion with PET+Al, but their total surface energies are so low that it might cause problems with ink wetting.

2.3. Suitability as the Substrate of a SC

2.3.1. Absorption

The amount of electrolyte in the SC is very small, and so even a small amount of it absorbing from the electrode into the substrate could affect the device's ability to function correctly. For this reason, the absorption of the water-based electrolyte and its components in the substrates was studied and is shown in **Figure 6** (Table S3, Supporting Information). The water-based electrolyte is composed of water and sodium chloride (NaCl). In order to prevent the water-based electrolyte from freezing when the SC is operated at below 0 °C conditions, an antifreeze agent such as glycerol can be added to the electrolyte.^[30] Therefore, the absorption of water, glycerol, salt water, and a mixture resembling the electrolyte were studied. When comparing the absorption results in Figure 6 to the structures of the polymers in Figure 2, the absorption of water appears to be

dependent on the ratio between polar and nonpolar segments in the polymer structures. The size of the nonpolar segment increases in order from PLA through PHB and PHBV to PET. The amount of water absorbed decreases in the same order, with PLA having absorbed the most water and PET+Al the least. PLA absorbs slightly less glycerol than it did water, likely due to glycerol's nonpolar carbon backbone, which makes it slightly less compatible with PLA. PHB and PHBV, however, absorb significantly less glycerol. This might be explained by the larger size of the glycerol molecule, as PHBV and especially PHB have high crystallinities (Table 1), and so the larger molecule would have a harder time diffusing into the tightly packed polymers. This phenomenon does not affect PLA, as it is amorphous. PET is also crystalline, but its crystallinity is significantly lower than that of PHB and PHBV, meaning the absorption lowering effect would also be smaller. Instead, the absorption of glycerol in PET+Al is higher than the absorption of water, which might be caused by the glycerol's nonpolar backbone improving its compatibility with PET. When comparing the amount of salt water absorbed by PLA and PHB to how much they absorbed water, it can be seen that the salt decreases the polymers' ability to absorb water very similarly, by 0.17 and 0.15 percentage units, respectively. Salt is a hygroscopic material, so it might be that some of the water molecules became bound to the sodium and chloride ions and were no longer available for absorption. However, in the case of PHBV, the presence of salt seems to have no effect on the absorption of water into the polymer. It was not possible to obtain reasonable absorption results for PET+Al, as the salt began

Figure 6. Absorption of A) water, B) glycerol, C) salt water, or D) a mixture of water, NaCl, and glycerol resembling the water-based electrolyte used in SCs in PLA, PHB, PHBV, and PET+Al.

penetrating the film at the interface between the PET and aluminum layers after about a week. This caused the absorption curve to increase linearly instead of plateauing. This happened even when the sample edges were protected with a layer of epoxy. One would expect the amount of electrolyte absorbed by a polymer to be somewhere between the amounts of glycerol and salt water absorbed by the same polymer. This is the case for PHB and PHBV, as well as for PET+Al when compared to glycerol and water, as no salt water absorption results were obtained for PET+Al, as mentioned. However, this is not the case for PLA, whose absorption of the electrolyte is much lower than the absorption of glycerol or salt water.

2.3.2. Barrier Properties

In order for a SC to function correctly, it must contain a certain minimum amount of electrolyte. No matter how good the barrier properties of the substrate are, some amount of the electrolyte is going to diffuse through it and evaporate during the SC's lifetime. The substrates studied here are intended for SCs with either water-based or Reline-based electrolyte, so the maximum amounts of electrolyte that can evaporate before the device stops working were estimated for evaluating substrates (calculations in

Supporting Information). These were 36.7 g for the water-based electrolyte and 22.2 g for the Reline-based electrolyte. The speed at which the substrate allows the electrolyte to evaporate is affected by the permeability of the substrate material as well as the thickness of the film.

The comparison in this study between the aluminum coated PET and the uncoated biopolymers is unfair in favor of PET+Al due to the additional aluminum layer, especially in the case of barrier properties. However, the choice of reference material was intentional, as PET+Al is the industry standard for substrates. As the aim of the study is to try to find a biobased substrate material to replace PET+Al and reduce the amount of the non-biobased aluminum used, the biopolymers are compared with PET+Al instead of uncoated PET.

The polymers' abilities to prevent electrolyte evaporation were assessed by studying their permeabilities under different conditions. At room temperature (23 °C), it can be seen that the WVP of PET+Al is the lowest due to the excellent barrier properties of the aluminum layer (**Figure 7A**). Additionally, the WVPs of PHB and PHBV are significantly lower than that of PLA, which is to be expected, as according to the previous literature PHB and PHBV have very good barrier properties due to their high crystallinities. Since the PLA studied here was amorphous, it was expected that its WVP would be high. For this reason, the WVP was also

Figure 7. Barrier properties of PLA, PHB, PHBV, and PET+Al A) against water vapor at room temperature, B) against water vapor at an elevated temperature, C) against water vapor at room temperature for samples that have been soaked in a mixture resembling the water-based electrolyte used in SCs, and D) against Reline at an elevated temperature.

determined for another, crystalline, PLA (crystallinity of 14.8%, estimated with DSC) to see how crystallinity would improve PLA's barrier properties. However, the crystallinity did not significantly improve the WVP, as the WVPs of amorphous and crystalline PLAs were 4.8×10^3 and 4.2×10^3 mg mm m⁻² day⁻¹, respectively. Permeabilities can be determined in many different conditions, so in order to compare the results more effectively with values found in literature, new values for WVP were calculated taking into account the partial pressure of water vapor (Table S4, Supporting Information). The values in this study are quite closely aligned with the values found in literature, though they are consistently slightly higher.

As mentioned, the operating temperatures of SCs can vary greatly, and since a material's permeability increases with temperature, the polymers' barrier properties against water were also studied at elevated temperatures (85 °C), as shown in Figure 7B. These conditions were too hot for PLA, which softened enough to break within the first 24 h. The order of the WVP values remains the same as at room temperature, where PET+Al had the lowest and PHBV the highest WVP. However, the increase in temperature has caused the WVPs to increase by approximately two orders of magnitude, as the free volume between the polymer chains increases with temperature, making permeation easier.

In order to prevent the water-based electrolyte from freezing when the SC is operated at below 0 °C conditions, an antifreeze agent such as glycerol can be added to the electrolyte. However, once it has absorbed into the substrate, glycerol can also act as a plasticizer in the polymer, which will decrease their barrier properties. As long as there is glycerol left in the electrolyte, an equilibrium of glycerol will be formed between the substrate and electrolyte, where new glycerol will be absorbed into the polymer to replace any that has evaporated out of the SC. The effect of glycerol on the barrier properties of the substrates was studied by soaking the samples in the same water-based electrolyte-like mixture used in the absorption tests and then measuring their WVPs (Figure 7C). The polymers behaved quite unexpectedly. The WVPs of PHB and PET+Al soaked in electrolyte increased, as expected, by 13% and 16%, respectively, compared to the WVPs of the films that had not been soaked in electrolyte (Figure 7A). However, the permeabilities of PLA and PHBV decreased by 11% and 22%, respectively. This was especially peculiar since soaking the samples in electrolyte caused the crystallinities of both PHB and PHBV to decrease by 4.8 percentage units from 68.2% and 61.0%, respectively. Crystallinity traditionally improves a film's barrier properties. Since their crystallinities decreased by the same amount, it would be anticipated that their permeabilities would also increase similarly. However, only PHB's permeability increased, so the changes in crystallinity do not explain the differences in how permeability changes.

To assess the substrates' ability to contain the Reline for the device's lifetime, their barriers against Reline were determined (Figure 7D). The test was done according to the gravimetric method as a wet cup test with Reline in the cups. The original intention was to test RP at room temperature and at an elevated temperature (80 °C). As the tests were done as wet cup tests, the expectation was for the mass to decrease as the Reline evaporated. However, at room temperature the RP was so low that the masses of the cups changed minimally, and when they

did, the mass tended to increase. During the room temperature test, the average conditions were 20.3 ± 0.4 °C/ 44.8 ± 6.4 RH. It is possible that the slight increase was caused by the moisture in the humid air being absorbed into the Reline, increasing its weight more than it decreased due to its evaporation. Thus, only the test at an elevated temperature gave reliable results. As with the WVP test at an elevated temperature, the conditions were too hot for PLA, and the films broke during the first 24 h. PET+Al continues to have superior barrier properties compared to the biopolymers, and out of the biopolymers, PHB still has the lower permeability. However, the RP of PHB is only about half of that of PHBV at an elevated temperature, whereas the WVPs of PHB and PHBV at an elevated temperature are very close to each other. Additionally, the RP values are about two orders of magnitude lower than the WVP values at high temperature, likely due to the Reline molecules being larger than the water molecules, making permeation more difficult.

As mentioned, the other aspect that influences electrolyte evaporation are the thicknesses of the films, which are not fixed values and can be adjusted during film processing. In order for a SC made of the substrate materials studied here to have a lifetime of a certain length, the substrate will need to have a certain minimum thickness in order to keep the electrolyte evaporation below the estimated maximum amount which will lead to the deterioration of the device, introduced earlier. These required substrate thicknesses are presented in Figure 8 for each of the polymers in different conditions and for a selection of different lifetimes (calculations in Supplemental Information). The appropriate thickness of the films is mainly governed by the roll-to-roll processability of the films, as they need to be flexible enough to be able to wind onto a roll. Most of the films have required thicknesses that are in no way sensible for roll-to-roll processing or SC production. An exception to this is the PET+Al film, which has a thin enough minimum thickness at all considered lifetimes when kept at room temperature (Figure 8A,C). Additionally, PET+Al film's thickness is also thin enough when calculated based on the WVP and RP at an elevated temperature for a SCs with lifetimes of 1 month, 6 months, or 1 year (Figure 8B,D). Outside of this, the required thicknesses of PET+Al films are unreasonable at elevated temperatures. PHB and PHBV also have reasonable thicknesses at room temperature for devices with a lifetime of 1 month (Figure 8A,C). However, their thicknesses at room temperature for all other lifetimes and at elevated temperatures (Figure 8B,D) are too thick. At room temperature PLA's thicknesses are unreasonable for all lifetimes and at elevated temperatures it fell apart completely, as mentioned.

It is important to note, however, that Figure 8 gives predictions of required substrate thicknesses in situations, where the conditions remain constant. Since in reality the temperature conditions during operation will be in constant flux, the thickness requirements given here are more guidelines than exact values.

Additionally, it has to be pointed out that when it is mentioned here that the thickness of the PET+Al film must be increased to improve the permeability, no statements can be made about how the thicknesses of the PET and aluminum layers should be changed. This is due to the fact that the PET+Al film was provided as film, and therefore the individual PET film and aluminum foil are not available for testing to see what their contributions to the permeability of the whole film are.

Figure 8. The required minimum substrate thicknesses of the SCs, if the lifetime is 1 month, 6 months, 1 year, 5 years, or 10 years, calculated with A) WVP at room temperature, B) WVP at elevated temperature, C) WVP at room temperature for samples soaked in electrolyte, and D) RP at elevated temperature.

Based on these results it can be seen that the biobased substrates do not fulfil the requirements for the lifetime of a SC nearly as well as the reference material PET+Al does. PET+Al had the lowest permeability under all studied conditions. Out of the biopolymers, PHB had the best barrier properties. Additionally, all films had a better barrier against Reline than against water, leading to thinner required substrate thicknesses for SCs made with Reline-based electrolyte.

It bears mentioning that the lifetimes of the SCs determined in this article are essentially the shelf lives of the devices. This means that the lifetime is based completely on the evaporation of the electrolyte, which is determined by the properties of the substrate. The lifetime consideration is not based on cyclic testing of the SC and therefore does not take into account the changes in the electrical properties of the SC over time.

3. Conclusion

The purpose of this study was to see how well biobased polymers would fulfil the requirements for SC substrates. Finding a biobased substrate for SCs would allow their development to move further toward sustainability.

All three of the studied biopolymers had sufficient processability. Their differences were shown more when it came to their printability. PLA's surface energy was slightly higher than that of PHB or PHBV, meaning it would more likely induce good wetting of the printing ink. However, its adhesion with the ink was lacking, whereas PHB and PHBV had perfect adhesion. To assess the substrates' behavior during the SC's lifetime, absorption tests were done, and it was found that all biopolymers absorbed less of the water-based electrolyte than the reference material PET+Al did. But the most important property of the substrate materials was their barriers against the electrolyte. The WVPs of the biopolymers were all too high to allow practical film thicknesses, especially at higher temperatures. The plasticizing effect of glycerol in the electrolyte caused the permeabilities of PHB and PET+Al to increase, but for PLA and PHBV the effect was the opposite. The RPs of the polymers were much better at elevated temperatures compared to the WVPs, but they were none the less too high.

None of the tested biopolymers performed well enough to be used in devices with longer lifetimes. However, out of these materials PHB is the most promising due to its relatively good barrier properties. To continue the development of a sustainable biobased SC substrate material, the substrate films ought to be

improved. This can be done by modifying the polymers to lower their permeabilities and by increasing the thicknesses of the films. WVP and RP can be reduced by mixing a filler into the polymer, which increases the tortuosity of the path a permeant molecule has to take while permeating through the material. The film thicknesses must be optimized in a way where they are thick enough to give good barrier properties but not too thick to interfere with roll-to-roll processing.

4. Experimental Section

Materials and Film Processing: Materials: Four different types of polymers were studied as possible substrate options, PLA, PHB, PHBV, and PET+Al. PET+Al was purchased as film from Pyroll Pakkukset Oy, Finland. The PLA pellets (Ingeo Biopolymer 4060D from NatureWorks LLC, United States) were purchased from Resinex Group, Finland, and the PHB and PHBV in powder form (ENMAT Y3000 and ENMAT Y1000, respectively, from Tianan Biologic Materials, China) were supplied by Helian Polymers BV, The Netherlands. The crystalline PLA films were provided by Centxebel, Belgium. The commercial graphite ink LOCTITE EDAG PF 407C E&C was from Henkel, Germany. NaCl, glycerol, and calcium chloride were purchased from VWR Chemicals. Water used in Mocon Aquatran Model 1 was purified with Millipore Milli-Q Direct 8; water used for other purposes was purified with Miele Aqua Purificator G 7895.

The Reline electrolyte was synthesized by combining choline chloride and urea in a molar ratio of 1:2. The mixture was then heated to 80 °C under constant stirring (VMS C7 Advanced, VWR) until a transparent and uniform liquid was obtained. After allowing it to cool to room temperature, the resulting liquid was employed as the electrolyte for the SC.^[31,32]

Materials and Film Processing: Film Production: To produce the biopolymer films, PHB and PHBV powders were first extruded into filaments using a Brabender DSE 25 twin screw extruder. The temperature setting of the extruder parts (barrel cylinders 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7, and adapter/die) was the same for PHB and PHBV, 160 °C/160 °C/170 °C/170 °C/170 °C/170 °C/170 °C/170 °C; the speed of the side feeder was 120 min⁻¹. The filaments were cut into pellets using a Brabender pelletizer. Finally, PLA, PHB, and PHBV pellets were all extruded into films using an Extrudex ED-N 30 single screw extruder. During extrusion, the screw speed was 15 rpm. The temperature settings for the extruder parts (barrel cylinders 1, 2, and 3, adapter, and die) were 200 °C/210 °C/210 °C/210 °C/200 °C for PLA with a melt temperature of 200 °C, and 180 °C/180 °C/180 °C/180 °C/175 °C for PHB and PHBV with melt temperatures of 175 °C.

Processability: Differential Scanning Calorimetry: DSC tests were done using Netzsch DSC 214 Polyma according to ISO 11357. Three parallel samples were tested for each material in a N₂ atmosphere with two heating scans per sample. The results were determined from the data of the second heating, except for the heat of fusion and crystallinity, which were determined from the first heating. The samples had been conditioned at 23 °C/50%RH for 48 h. The PET+Al samples were heated from 0 to 350 °C at 10 K min⁻¹, PLA was heated from 0 to 270 °C at 10 K min⁻¹, and PHB and PHBV were heated from 0 °C to 200 °C at 5 K min⁻¹. The enthalpies of melting of a 100% crystalline polymer were 140 J g⁻¹ for PET^[33] and 146 J g⁻¹ for PHB^[8] and PHBV.^[34] The type of crystalline PLA was not known, so its crystallinity was estimated by using 93.1 J g⁻¹ as the enthalpy of melting of a 100% crystalline PLA.^[35]

Processability: Dynamic Mechanical Analysis: DMA was done to determine the glass transition temperatures for PHB and PHBV since they could not be determined from the DSC curves. The tests were done using PerkinElmer Pyris Diamond DMA in tension mode with one sample per material. The dimensions of the samples were 20 × 4 mm. The temperature was increased from 25 to 100 °C at 3 °C min⁻¹ and the frequency was 1 Hz.

Processability: Thermogravimetric Analysis: TGA was done using Netzsch TG 209 F3 Tarsus according to ISO 11358. Three parallel samples per material were conditioned at 23 °C/50%RH for 48 h and tested in a N₂

atmosphere. The samples were heated from 35 to 600, 470, 360, or 400 °C for PET+Al, PLA, PHB, or PHBV, respectively, at a heating rate of 10 K min⁻¹.

Processability: Necking: Necking of the extruded films was determined by measuring the width of the finished films and then subtracting that width from the width of the extruder die, which was 15 cm. The width of the film was calculated as an average of width measurements done once per meter of film. The results were presented as percentages of the original width.

Processability: Tensile Properties: Tensile properties of the films were determined using Testometric M500 according to ISO 527. The samples had dimensions of 25 × 150 mm with a 50 mm gauge length and were conditioned at 23 °C/50%RH for 24 h. The tests were only done in machine direction, since the films were not wide enough to make 150 mm long samples in the cross direction. The average thicknesses of the films were measured with Mitutoyo Digimatic caliper, and were 0.07, 0.26, 0.43, and 0.06 mm, for PLA, PHB, PHBV, and PET+Al, respectively. Testing was done using a 250 kgf load cell and at a test speed of 25 mm min⁻¹. Six samples were tested for each material, and the tensile properties were determined from the samples of successful tests, which included four samples for PHB, five samples for PHBV, and six samples for PET+Al and PLA. Strength, strain at strength, stress at break, and strain at break were determined from the results according to ISO 527-1. The very beginning of the stress-strain curve has a slight curvature to it, so the tensile modulus was determined as the slope of the middle of the linear section using the least squares method, as this would give a more accurate understanding of the modulus.

Processability: Flexural Properties: Flexural properties were measured with Instron 5967 universal testing system according to ISO 178. 5 samples with dimensions of 25 × 70 mm were cut and conditioned at 23 °C/50%RH for 24 h. Flexural tests were also only done in the machine direction. PET+Al samples were tested so that the aluminum side experienced the tensile stress, as the brittle aluminum is more sensitive to tension than PET is. The film thicknesses (Mitutoyo Digimatic caliper) were 0.09, 0.25, 0.42, and 0.06 mm for PLA, PHB, PHBV, and PET+Al, respectively. The test was done as a three-point bending test with a 500 N load cell. Support span was 12 mm, support diameter was 4 mm, and loading edge diameter was 6 mm. Strength was determined according to ISO 178. Flexural modulus was determined from the slope of the linear section at the beginning of the curve.

Printability: Surface Energies: Contact angles were measured using the Krüss DSA100S drop shape analyzer according to ISO 19403-2. The test was done according to the sessile drop method with 12 drops of 6 µL per sample with two liquids, water and ethylene glycol. As the extruded PHB and PHBV films had slightly uneven surfaces, they were first pressed flat by sandwiching them between two glass plates and placing them in an oven (Termaks) at 190 °C until they melted, after which the smooth films were peeled off the plates. All samples were conditioned at 23 °C/50%RH for 24 h. The surface energies were calculated based on the contact angles according to ISO 19403-2 using the Owens-Wendt-Rabel-Kaelble method.

Printability: Ink Adhesion: Tape tests were done according to ASTM D3359-17. Films were coated with a commercial graphite ink using a coating device (MTV Messtechnik CX 4 motorized film applicator) and a doctor blade. After coating the ink was dried in an oven (VWR VENTI-Line VL 56 Prime) at 95 °C for 1 h. The samples were conditioned at 23 °C/50%RH for 14 days before testing. The tape used was Elcometer 99 and was pressed onto the test area using a rubber roller.

Suitability as the Substrate of a SC: Absorption: Absorption of four different liquids by the films was determined according to ISO 62. The films were cut into square samples with dimensions of 6 cm × 6 cm. The average thicknesses (measured with Mitutoyo IP54 digital micrometer) of the samples were 0.113 ± 0.043, 0.279 ± 0.030, 0.429 ± 0.030, and 0.062 ± 0.001 cm for PLA, PHB, PHBV, and PET+Al, respectively. The samples were first dried in an oven (Termaks) at 50 °C for 72 h. The liquids were water, glycerol, salt water (1 M NaCl), and a mixture resembling the water-based electrolyte made of water (55 v-%), glycerol (45 v-%), and NaCl (1 M). Three parallel samples of a film were immersed in 900 mL of each liquid. The samples were weighed 24, 48, 96, 19, and 384 h after

the beginning of the test. The excess liquid was first wiped off the surfaces of samples before weighing them with Precisa EP 220A and re-immersing in the liquid. The final absorbed amount of liquid was calculated as an average of the plateau region, which consisted of the last three data points of the test (96, 192, and 384 h).

Suitability as the Substrate of a SC: Barrier Properties: The sizes of the permeability samples were 50 cm² for PET+Al, and 5 cm² for PLA, PHB and PHBV, as the biopolymer films were too narrow to cut bigger samples. The smaller samples were made by sandwiching a piece of the film between two aluminum masks with 5 cm² holes in the middle. In WVP tests, at room temperature the crystalline PLA was tested with 50 cm² samples. The thicknesses of the films were measured with a Mitutoyo IP54 digital micrometer. The conditions the tests were done in were chosen so that the concentration of water or Reline vapor in the air would be as high as possible to try to emulate the situation when the substrate is placed next to liquid electrolyte, hence the high relative humidities.

Suitability as the Substrate of a SC: Barrier Properties—Coulometric Method: The WVPs at room temperature and WVPs of samples soaked in electrolyte were measured with the coulometric method according to ISO 15106-3 using Mocon Aquatran Model 1 water vapor transmission rate test system. Both tests were done at 23 °C/100%RH. The samples were conditioned for 12 h in the instrument before the tests. For the room temperature test, the PHBV sample was conditioned at 23 °C/70%RH for 7 days before inserting in the instrument, as the film was quite thick and without this step the water vapor transmission rate took too long to plateau. For the test on electrolyte-soaked samples, the samples were immersed in a mixture resembling the water-based electrolyte made of water (55 v-%), glycerol (45 v-%), and NaCl (1 M). Immersing the aluminum layer of the PET+Al film into the electrolyte had previously been found to cause corrosion, so the film was only soaked from the PET side. This was done by clamping the film between a flat aluminum base and an aluminum ring with a diameter of about 11 cm. The film was placed with the PET side toward the ring and the electrolyte was poured into the “cup” created by the ring and base. The films were soaked until saturated, after which they were wiped clean and inserted in the water vapor transmission rate test system. The WVP measured with the coulometric method were determined as averages of the data points in the second half of the plateau region of the time-transmission rate curve.

Suitability as the Substrate of a SC: Barrier Properties—Gravimetric Method: The WVPs and RPs at an elevated temperature were measured with the gravimetric method according to ISO 2528. The WVP test at an elevated temperature was done in a climate cabinet (Espec PR-2J) at 85 °C/98%RH, which is the cabinet's highest operating temperature and humidity. The climate cabinet does not allow solvents, so the RP tests were done in an oven (Termaks) with ventilation to the outside to remove any solvent vapors. The conditions during the RP test were monitored with an EasyLog EL-USB-2+ data logger and the average conditions were found to be 80.1 ± 1.0 °C/4.2 ± 0.8%RH. The temperature for the Reline test was chosen based on the maximum operating temperature of the data logger, which was 80 °C. The high temperature tests were done as dry cup tests and the desiccant in the cups was calcium chloride. The tests with Reline were done as wet cup tests with 10 mL of Reline in the cups. Due to PET+Al's low expected WVP, two blank assemblies were used for PET+Al in the high temperature test. The RP was expected to be quite low for all materials, so in the Reline test blank assemblies were used for all materials. The cups were weighed every 24 h for 10 days. The balance used for weighing during gravimetric tests was Precisa EP 220A. The WVP and RP measured with the gravimetric method were determined according to ISO 2528.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the SUINK project funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No. 101070112. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Parts of the research used the Research Council of Finland Research Infrastructure “Printed Intelligence Infrastructure.” The authors would also like to thank Tommi Lehtinen for assisting with film processing and Jukka Koskinen for performing the DMA analysis.

Open access publishing facilitated by Tampereen yliopisto ja Tampereen ammattikorkeakoulu, as part of the Wiley - FinELib agreement.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

Research data are not shared.

Keywords

barrier properties, biobased substrates, printed electronics, printing properties, supercapacitors, sustainable electronics

Received: August 27, 2025

Revised: November 12, 2025

Published online:

- [1] Y.-Z. Zhang, Y. Wang, T. Cheng, L. Q. Yao, X. Li, W. Y. Lai, W. Huang, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2019**, *48*, 3229.
- [2] R. Liu, Z. L. Wang, K. Fukuda, T. Someya, *Nat. Rev. Mater.* **2022**, *7*, 870.
- [3] Y. C. Goswami, S. Begzaad, *Energy Storage* **2024**, *6*, e666.
- [4] J. Son, H. Kim, Y. Choi, H. Lee, *Microsyst. Nanoeng.* **2024**, *10*, 1.
- [5] C. Reyes, E. Fivaz, Z. Sajó, A. Schneider, G. Siqueira, J. Ribera, A. Poulin, F. W. M. R. Schwarze, G. Nyström, *ACS Sustainable Chem. Eng.* **2024**, *12*, 16001.
- [6] S. Farah, D. G. Anderson, R. Langer, *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.* **2016**, *107*, 367.
- [7] A. L. Rivera-Briso, Á. Serrano-Aroca, *Polymers* **2018**, *10*, 732.
- [8] A. J. dos Santos, L. V. O. D. Valentina, A. A. H. Schulz, M. A. T. Duarte, *Ing. Cienc.* **2017**, *13*, 269.
- [9] I. N. Najjar, P. Sharma, R. Das, K. Mondal, A. K. Singh, S. Tamang, P. Hazra, N. Thakur, R. Bhanwaria, S. G. Gandhi, V. Kumar, *Food Bioprod. Process.* **2024**, *148*, 11.
- [10] A. Jin, L. J. del Valle, J. Puiggalí, *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **2023**, *24*, 17250.
- [11] M. Brtnicky, V. Pecina, J. Holatko, T. Hammerschmiedt, A. Mustafa, A. Kintl, J. Fojt, T. Baltazar, J. Kucerik, *Chem. Biol. Technol. Agric.* **2022**, *9*, 75.
- [12] R. W. Brown, D. R. Chadwick, H. Zang, M. Graf, X. Liu, K. Wang, L. M. Greenfield, D. L. Jones, *J. Hazard. Mater.* **2023**, *441*, 129959.
- [13] A. F. Sousa, C. Vilela, M. Matos, C. S. R. Freire, A. J. D. Silvestre, J. F. J. Coelho, in *Poly(Ethylene Terephthalate) Based Blends, Composites and Nanocomposites*, (Eds: P. M. Visakh, M. Liang), William Andrew Publishing, Oxford **2015**, pp. 113–141.

- [14] J. K. Muiruri, J. C. C. Yeo, H. Run, T. T. Lin, X. Hou, V. Raveenkumar, B. Y. Jian, W. Thitsartarn, C. He, Z. Li, *Eur. Polym. J.* **2024**, *210*, 112926.
- [15] H. de Beukelaer, M. Hilhorst, Y. Workala, E. Maaskant, W. Post, *Polym. Test.* **2022**, *116*, 107803.
- [16] S. Torres-Giner, L. Hilliou, B. Meléndez-Rodríguez, K. J. Figueroa-Lopez, D. Madalena, L. Cabedo, J. A. Covas, A. A. Vicente, J. M. Lagaron, *Food Packag. Shelf Life* **2018**, *17*, 39.
- [17] B. Meléndez-Rodríguez, S. Torres-Giner, M. A. M. Reis, F. Silva, M. Matos, L. Cabedo, J. M. Lagarón, *Polymers* **2021**, *13*, 1155.
- [18] M. Avella, E. Martuscelli, M. Raimo, *J. Mater. Sci.* **2000**, *35*, 523.
- [19] *Ingeo Biopolymer 4060D Technical Data Sheet For Heat Seal Layer in Coextruded Oriented Film.*
- [20] E. Lizundia, M. C. Penayo, A. Guinault, J. L. Vilas, S. Domenek, *Polym. Test.* **2019**, *75*, 175.
- [21] K. Litauszki, Z. Kovács, L. Mészáros, Á. Kmetty, *Polym. Test.* **2019**, *76*, 411.
- [22] J. Greener, G. Pearson, M. Cakmak, *Roll-To-Roll Manufacturing: Process Elements And Recent Advances*, John Wiley & Sons, Incorporated, Newark, USA, **2018**, <http://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/tampere/detail.action?docID=5313447> (accessed: June 2024).
- [23] C. Tóth, N. L. Lukács, N. K. Kovács, *Polym. Compos.* **2024**, *45*, 13589.
- [24] H. Oguz, C. Dogan, D. Kara, Z. T. Ozen, D. Ovali, M. Nofar, *AIP Conf. Proc.* **2019**, *2055*, 030003.
- [25] J. Chen, D. Wu, K. Pan, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* **2016**, *88*, 120.
- [26] Y. W. Kwon, T. J. Wentworth, C.-M. Park, *Multiscale Multidiscip. Model. Exp. Des.* **2025**, *8*, 378.
- [27] D. Leguillon, É. Martin, M.-C. Lafarie-Frenot, *C. R. Méc.* **2015**, *343*, 275.
- [28] M. Alharbi, R. D. Bairwan, W. Y. Rizg, H. A. Khalil, S. S. Murshid, A. M. Sindi, M. Alissa, N. I. Saharudin, C. K. Abdullah, *Polym. Compos.* **2024**, *45*, 9317.
- [29] J. Wiklund, A. Karakoç, T. Palko, H. Yiğitler, K. Ruttik, R. Jäntti, J. Paltakari, *J. Manuf. Mater. Process.* **2021**, *5*, 89.
- [30] A. Railanmaa, S. Lehtimäki, J. Keskinen, D. Lupo, *Sci. Rep.* **2019**, *9*, 14059.
- [31] C. Mevada, J. Tissari, V. S. Parihar, A. Tewari, J. Keskinen, M. Kellomäki, M. Mäntysalo, *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2024**, *12*, 24357.
- [32] C. Mevada, J. Tissari, V. S. Parihar, A. Tewari, J. Keskinen, M. Mäntysalo, *J. Power Sources* **2024**, *624*, 235529.
- [33] D. Heidrich, M. Gehde, *Polymers* **2022**, *14*, 793.
- [34] S. Kennouche, N. Le Moigne, M. Kaci, J. C. Quantin, A. S. Caro-Bretelle, C. Delaite, J. M. Lopez-Cuesta, *Eur. Polym. J.* **2016**, *75*, 142.
- [35] L.-T. Lim, R. Auras, M. Rubino, *Prog. Polym. Sci.* **2008**, *33*, 820.
- [36] M. Arvani, J. Keskinen, D. Lupo, M. Honkanen, *J. Energy Storage* **2020**, *29*, 101384.